

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KIM****FIRST NAME: UN YONG****PROGRAM CODE: DIFE****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MS Word – Office 365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. For any academic essays, there are some basic structures to follow. What is the most reasonable step-by-step approach to completing the essay chronologically?
- Analyze, research, peer-review, literature review, drafting, check references, and submission.
 - Analyze, establish arguments, research, literature review, developing, editing, peer-review, check references, and submission.¹**
 - Analyze, check references, research, structuring, editing, review, and submission.
 - Analyze, preliminary reading, organizing, planning, redrafting, and submission.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7-10.

2. After understanding the main topic, the author needs to conduct extensive research to ensure that the author gives the supporting knowledge and evidence to develop the overall thesis. Which of the following is the most appropriate question to ask before undertaking the research work?
- Is a particular piece of writing in a journal easy to understand for my argument?
 - In which order do I need to discuss the relevant supporting points?
 - What kind of resources should I look for to write the essay?**²
 - What kind of knowledge will I gain after research?
3. Select an answer that best describes a situation when a citation is necessary and thus required.
- An author paraphrases the main ideas from a specific source.**³
 - An author creates or suggests a new idea in addition to all previous work.
 - Such citations point readers to sources that are relevant to the argument.
 - A commonsensical statement is used by an author.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 8-14.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 140.

4. The book "Turabian Rule of Style" emphasizes the importance of having a proper plan before getting to write any essay. Which of the following is the most appropriate response that she would give while preparing for such essay writing?
- Finding sources for the pure purpose of citation only.
 - Reading much more than necessary to have perfect knowledge on the research topic.
 - Prepare at least five drafts consecutively before revising them.
 - Trying to put oneself in the shoes of readers when devising a writing plan.⁴**
5. Argument construction is, without a doubt, an essential part of writing an essay, according to Turabian. Which of the following is the most accurate statement that describes one of the steps when constructing an argument?
- Ignoring what potential readers might think about a research topic.
 - Converting one's hypothesis into a claim by having a backing reason, evidence, acknowledgment, and warrant.⁵**
 - Having a warrant-based argument in the essay rather than an evidence-based one.
 - Testing every hypothesis from the literature review.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 10-134.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 56-67.

6. According to Turabian, there are two types of style for citing sources — author-date style and notes-bibliography style. Which of the following is considered a notes-bibliography style, not an author-date one?

- Hayes, Romain. 2011. *Subhas Chandra Bose in Nazi Germany: Politics, Intelligence, and Propaganda, 1941–43*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Jane Austen, *Mansfield Park: An Annotated Edition*, ed. Deidre Shauna Lynch (Cambridge, MA: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2016).**⁶
- Choi, Susanne Y. P., and Yinni Peng. 2016. *Masculine Promise: Migration, Family, and Gender in China*. Oakland: University of California Press.
- Duckworth, Angela. 2016. *Grit: The Power of Passion and Perseverance*. New York: Scribner.

7. Which of the following is considered essential in a typical dissertation, according to Bloomberg and Volpe?

- Arguments and Evidence.
- Synthesis of Findings.**⁷
- Methodological History.
- Recommended Peer Review Journals.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 147-300.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018), 1-89.

8. Knowledge claims imply many assumptions about what the researcher will learn during the inquiry. In other words, these are research paradigms or worldviews. According to Bloomberg and Volpe, which of the following is the correct statement regarding those knowledge claims?
- Pragmatism: all knowledge is based on antecedent conditions.
 - Interpretivism: all knowledge can be found within a certain social circle.
 - Critical Theory: all knowledge is based on criticisms arising from corrupt politicians.
 - Post-positivism: all knowledge can be derived from direct observation.⁸**
9. According to Bloomberg and Volpe, which of the following is the most accurate statement on the function, purpose, role, or scope of the literature review.
- Its purpose is to provide a clear and balanced picture of unrelated theories.
 - Its role is to merely criticize others' work before writing an essay.
 - Its function is to support research and articulate those in an integrated way.⁹**
 - Its scope is around one or two conceptual frameworks that investigate one problem.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 146-150.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 352-359.

10. According to Bloomberg and Volpe, which research methodology is best recommended when some pattern-induced data vastly supports a particular behavioral phenomenon?

- Action research.
- Ethnography.
- Grounded theory.**¹⁰
- Phenomenology.

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 256-280.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.